

TITLE: COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF TRADITIONAL METHODS AND BIM 5D IN COST ESTIMATION FOR ELECTRICAL PROJECTS

SUBMITTED: 2026, February

ORCID iD: 0009-0000-1765-9758

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18489213

Giovany Corsini Santos, Electrical Engineer;

Graduate Certificate in Building Information Modeling (BIM);

PUCRS - Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre, Brazil

giovany.corsini@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

*The use of the BIM methodology has been consolidating as an essential practice in the global construction industry, mainly due to its ability to integrate different disciplines into a single digital model, promoting greater accuracy, efficiency, and cost savings throughout the project life cycle. This study aims to comparatively analyze the methods of quantification and cost estimation in electrical projects through three distinct approaches: traditional manual takeoff, quantity extraction using AutoCAD 2D, and the application of Revit with **BIM 5D** features. The research is based on a real case study of electrical installation budgeting, typical of the author's professional practice.*

*The methodology is applied in nature, combining qualitative and quantitative approaches, with a comparative **performance** analysis among the methods. Criteria such as execution time, quantify accuracy, risk of human error, and ease of project updating will be considered.*

*The expected results include demonstrating the **advantages** of BIM in the electrical budgeting process, especially regarding data reliability and time efficiency. Therefore, this study contributes to the ongoing discussion on the digitalization of the electrical sector in construction, offering practical insights for professionals and companies **transitioning** to the BIM environment.*

Keywords: *Electrical, BIM 5D, Performance, Advantages, Transitioning*

Preprint statement: *This manuscript is a preprint distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).*

1. INTRODUCTION

The construction industry has been undergoing a continuous process of transformation with the advancement of technologies applied to project design, execution, and construction management. Within this context, the Building Information Modeling (BIM) methodology has emerged as a disruptive innovation, enabling the integration of graphical and non-graphical data into intelligent three-dimensional models. By centralizing information and enabling coordination between disciplines, BIM has been increasingly adopted by companies seeking greater accuracy and efficiency in project development processes.

Many professionals in the field have been migrating from traditional methods, such as manual takeoffs and the use of 2D CAD, to solutions that promote automation, interdisciplinary coordination, and improved project visualization. This transition still faces challenges, such as the learning curve and implementation costs, but the gains in productivity and technical quality justify the investment in the medium term.

Among the features offered by the methodology, BIM 5D stands out for integrating cost information into the three-dimensional model, allowing quantities to be automatically extracted based on the modeling performed in the software. This feature is especially useful in electrical projects, where the accuracy of component takeoffs directly affects budgeting and execution. In addition to reducing errors and rework, the use of BIM contributes to more complete and reliable documentation, facilitating revisions and adjustments throughout the design process. The organization by categories, the dynamic updating of schedules, and the clarity of the generated information strengthen the role of the electrical engineer in the technical and financial planning of the project.

This study proposes a comparative analysis of takeoff and quantification methods based on the BIM methodology. The choice of this focus aims to investigate, from a practical perspective, how the adoption of BIM impacts execution time, data reliability, and the overall efficiency of the electrical cost estimation process. Through this comparison, the study seeks to understand to what extent BIM can improve the traditional workflow and what barriers still hinder its broader adoption among professionals and medium-sized companies.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Cost Estimation and BIM

The cost estimation of electrical projects is a technically and financially critical stage in the development of any construction project. However, this activity is often carried out manually, using measurements taken from printed drawings with traditional tools such as scale rulers, markers, and calculators, or through software like AutoCAD, which makes the process faster but still far from achieving maximum efficiency in terms of time and error reduction. Although these methods remain common in the industry, they are prone to human error, difficulties in updating, and inconsistencies between drawings and budgets where much of what is not »visible« in a 2D drawing is often quantified based on the estimator's assumptions. According to Lu et al. (2015), the use of BIM in electrical and mechanical systems not only improves cost estimation accuracy but also reduces coordination errors, providing greater reliability to the project.

With the advancement of BIM, especially in its 5D dimension, it has become possible to integrate project design with real-time cost estimation, providing greater reliability for planning and execution. This research is justified by the need to practically assess the advantages and limitations of BIM 5D compared to conventional methods used by electrical engineers in corporate environments.

Building Information Modeling (BIM) is a methodology that enables the development and management of projects through digital three-dimensional models enriched with data and information. BIM is not merely a graphical representation but an information integration system that encompasses all phases of a building's life cycle: conception, planning, execution, operation, and maintenance.

According to Eastman et al. (2011), “BIM is a model-based approach that provides consistent, coordinated, and computable information about a building in design or operation.” Unlike CAD, which works with lines and two-dimensional representations with indirect information, BIM allows the creation of parametric elements (walls, luminaires, panels, conduits, etc.) that carry physical, functional, and financial attributes.

In addition, BIM facilitates collaborative work among different disciplines (architecture, structural, electrical, and plumbing), promoting greater control, transparency, and early detection of conflicts.

2.2 BIM Levels of Development

In the BIM environment, there are several levels of modeling, data, and functionality development, as follows:

BIM 3D: Known for three-dimensional modeling, it facilitates the visualization of structures and the coordination of different disciplines.

BIM 4D: Integrates 3D modeling with construction scheduling and planning, allowing the connection between development phases and the established timeline. Through compatible software, it is possible to simulate each stage of the construction process in a realistic time-lapse format, helping visualize what is to come.

BIM 5D: Builds upon the previous levels by adding cost elements. In 5D, each modeled component has an associated cost, enabling quick and updated estimates as the project evolves.

BIM 6D: Focuses on energy efficiency, performance simulation, and sustainability. With BIM 6D, it becomes possible to meet Green Building and LEED certification criteria depending on the project.

BIM 7D: At this stage, the model becomes an asset for facility management of the completed building, providing maintenance teams with comprehensive information such as equipment maintenance schedules, manuals, warranties, and the 3D model itself.

Although still under development and lacking a global standard, additional levels have been proposed: BIM 8D for occupational safety, BIM 9D for Lean Construction, BIM 10D for modularization and industrialization processes, BIM 11D for resilience, and BIM 12D for Smart Cities.

However, for the purposes of this study, the so-called “fifth dimension” of BIM — BIM 5D — refers specifically to the integration of cost data into the 3D model. From the three-dimensional modeling, it is possible to automatically extract quantities and associate unit prices, enabling real-time budget simulations based on the actual and updated design.

In a study by researchers from the University of Liverpool on project management and BIM, state that the use of BIM 5D can significantly reduce rework and improve cost estimation accuracy, as reported by Bryde et al. (2013).

In integrated project environments, any change made to the model (such as replacing a conduit or luminaire) is automatically reflected in the quantity schedules and total estimated cost. This creates a direct relationship between design and budgeting, facilitating both technical and financial decision-making.

2.3 Implementation Challenges

Despite the numerous benefits associated with the adoption of BIM, its effective implementation still faces significant challenges, especially in developing countries such as Brazil. These barriers can be technical, financial, cultural, or organizational in nature and often determine the pace at which companies transition from traditional methods to integrated digital workflows.

- **High Implementation Costs:**
The initial investment in software licenses, hardware upgrades, and specialized training can be a major obstacle, particularly for small and medium-sized companies. The return on investment (ROI) is often medium- to long-term, which discourages immediate adoption.

- **Lack of Qualified Professionals:**
There is still a shortage of professionals with practical experience in BIM tools and workflows, especially in disciplines such as electrical and mechanical systems. This knowledge gap delays implementation and increases dependence on external consultants.
- **Resistance to Change:**
The transition from 2D CAD processes to 3D BIM environments demands a cultural shift within organizations. Professionals accustomed to traditional methods may resist adopting new workflows due to the learning curve or fear of reduced productivity during the adaptation period.
- **Absence of Standardization:**
Although international standards such as ISO 19650 provide guidelines for information management, many companies still lack internal BIM protocols and execution plans. The absence of standardized modeling criteria leads to inconsistencies and coordination difficulties among project participants.
- **Software Interoperability:**
Different disciplines often use distinct software platforms, and lack of full compatibility between them can result in information loss or rework when exchanging models. The need for interoperable formats (such as IFC) remains a critical issue in multidisciplinary collaboration.
- **Management and Process Integration:**
Implementing BIM goes beyond using software—it requires rethinking workflows, redefining responsibilities, and integrating departments such as engineering, budgeting, and facilities management. Without process alignment, BIM may be underutilized or used only for visualization purposes.
- **Limited Institutional and Client Demand:**
Many clients, especially in the private sector, still do not require BIM deliverables, which reduces the incentive for companies to fully adopt the methodology. Government initiatives and public policies mandating BIM are gradually changing this scenario but remain unevenly applied.

In summary, the challenges in BIM implementation are not purely technological but also managerial and cultural. Overcoming these barriers requires long-term commitment, investment in professional training, and the establishment of standardized processes to fully exploit BIM's potential across all stages of construction project development.

Although BIM is already well established in fields such as architecture and structural design, its application in electrical installations is still overlooked by a considerable portion of builders. Despite all the challenges, the use of BIM represents a real opportunity for significant improvement in construction processes. Revit MEP is one of the most widely used software tools for this purpose, allowing the creation of complete electrical systems with panels, circuits, devices, and conduit pathways.

Among its most notable features are:

- 3D modeling of electrical elements with spatial accuracy;
- Placement of conduits and wiring;
- Calculation of total load and demand;
- Coordination with other disciplines;
- Automatic generation of quantify schedules (number of outlets, meters of conduit etc.)

Amorim and Teixeira (2019) report that the use of BIM in electrical projects facilitates visualization, clash detection, and more accurate cost estimation through the integration of modeling and cost control.

According to Chen and Luo (2014), the use of BIM in quality management models allows for the detection of design flaws during the project phase, significantly reducing rework and inconsistencies during construction.

Furthermore, the ability to identify conflicts with plumbing and structural systems during the design phase greatly reduces the occurrence of errors on-site.

3. OBJECTIVES AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This research seeks to answer the following question:

How can the application of BIM 5D optimize time, reduce errors, and improve cost estimation accuracy in electrical installation projects compared to traditional methods and AutoCAD ?

3.1 General Objective

To evaluate the efficiency and accuracy of BIM 5D in the cost estimation of electrical projects by comparing it with traditional manual and CAD-based methods.

3.1.1 Specific Objectives

To carry out the quantity takeoff of an electrical project using:

- (a) The traditional/manual method by entering quantities into a spreadsheet;
- (b) AutoCAD, using commands such as bcount and tlen, entering the quantities into a spreadsheet;
- (c) Revit, with a focus on BIM 5D, generating automatic quantities ready to be inserted into the spreadsheet.

Compare the results of the three methods based on:

- Execution time;
- Quantity errors;
- Ease of updating;
- Accuracy of budget data;
- Identify the advantages and limitations of using BIM in electrical installations for residential, commercial, and building projects.

4. METHODOLOGY

This study is characterized as applied research with a qualitative and quantitative approach, using a case study strategy. The object of analysis will be a real electrical installation project in a corporate building, originally developed in AutoCAD. The methodology will be applied in three approaches:

1. Manual takeoff of quantities;
2. Quantity takeoff using AutoCAD with counting and length measurement commands;
3. Modeling in Revit (BIM 5D), with automated extraction of quantities.

The comparative analysis between the methods will consider criteria such as execution time, data accuracy, ease of revision, and potential for error reduction. The study will also include graphs and tables to visualize the results, as well as a detailed execution schedule.

5. CASE STUDY DESCRIPTION

The case study refers to the electrical installation project of a high-end residential building in São Paulo, Brazil. The values presented are also expressed in Brazilian Reais (R\$), the local currency..

For the scientific research, three real scenarios were carried out by the author of this study with the aim of reproducing the daily routine of an electrical cost estimator. Timed quantity takeoffs were performed using a

real electrical project of a high-end house with a usable area of 279.1 m² (3,004 sq ft) distributed over two floors.

6. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

6.1 Description of Each Scenario

Scenario 1:

Figure 1: Organizational chart scenario 1.

In this scenario, the traditional method was used, where the project to be estimated is received, all its sheets are printed, and then each item is analyzed, measured, and counted. After this process, all quantities are entered into an existing spreadsheet that automatically calculates the final values for materials and labor, also allowing for the adjustment of O&P (overhead and profit).

In this case, the time required to print and take off the quantities was 90 minutes, after which entering the quantities into the spreadsheet took approximately 30 minutes. Considering the process from start to the formalization of the budget for delivery, the average total time was 120 minutes.

After completing the entire process of quantity takeoff and entering data into the spreadsheet, a double-check was performed comparing the spreadsheet entries with the project. A total of 5 errors were identified: 2 related to the length of infrastructure, 1 related to circuit length, and 2 related to the number of outlets and switches.

Spreadsheet used for calculating materials and labor through the manual method:

Item	Service	Quant.	Unit.	Sub MAT R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
LABOR AND MATERIALS SUPPLY						
Manager:	Anonymous					
Project:	Anonymous					
Resp. Manag.:						
PRICE SUMMARY OF ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE						
1	ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE - FIRST FLOOR	1	VB	26,639.69	56,035.96	82,674.65
2	ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE - SECOND FLOOR	1	VB	17,578.40	57,634.63	75,213.03
3	ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE - FEEDERS - GENERAL IMPLEMENTATION	1	VB	6,818.52	32,563.59	39,382.11
				EXECUTION TIME (DAYS): 60		
				PAYMENT METHOD : TO COMBINE		
CONSIDERATIONS:						
EXCLUSIONS:						
1 - luminaires, lamps, ballasts and accessories.						
2 - generator set, UPS, transformer, stabilizer and related accessories.						
3 - civil construction services in general.						
4 - structured cabling services, CCTV systems, access control, fire detection and alarm, sound, etc.						
GENERAL TOTAL				51,035.61	146,174.18	197,209.79

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS AND INFRASTRUCTURE - OUTLETS										
FIRST FLOOR										
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL										
							1,007.20		12,598.29	13,605.49
1		BOLTNUT/WASHER ø 1/4"		380	CJ	0.84	319.20	15.12	5,744.82	6,064.02
2		REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE	REAL PERFIL INOVA	80	M	8.60	688.00	85.67	6,853.47	7,541.47
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL										
							3,849.61		12,374.55	16,224.15
1		COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX. #2.50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX	NAMBEI	384	M	4.54	1,741.54	15.12	5,799.25	7,540.79
2		COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX. #4.00mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX	NAMBEI	70	M	6.74	471.80	20.16	1,411.01	1,882.81
3		COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX. #6.00mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX	NAMBEI	171	M	9.58	1,636.26	39.24	5,164.29	6,800.56
FINISHES SUBTOTAL										
							1,164.40		5,291.26	6,455.68
1		4"X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 OUTLET 2P-T-10A - MODEL THESY	INOVA	10	PC	44.16	441.60	201.57	2,015.73	2,457.33
2		4"X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 2 OUTLETS 2P-T-10A - MODEL THESY	INOVA	10	PC	72.28	722.80	327.56	3,275.56	3,998.36
TOTAL COST										
							6,021.21		30,264.12	36,285.33

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS - LIGHTING										
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL										
							1,402.76		11,136.89	12,239.67
1		REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE	INOVA	90	M	8.60	774.00	85.67	7,710.15	8,484.15
2		BOLTNUT/WASHER ø 1/4"	REAL PERFIL	100	CJ	0.84	84.00	15.12	1,511.79	1,595.79
3		4"X4" PVC OCTAGONAL BOX	INOVA	8	PC	26.40	211.20	201.57	1,612.58	1,823.78
4		4"X2" PVC BOX	INOVA	3	PC	5.86	17.58	100.79	302.36	319.94
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL										
							916.26		3,047.78	3,964.04
1		COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX. #2.50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX	NAMBEI	202	M	4.54	916.26	15.12	3,047.78	3,964.04
FINISHES SUBTOTAL										
							1,599.44		5,820.41	7,419.85
1		4"X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 SINGLE-POLE 2p SWITCH - THESY LINE - WHITE	INOVA	8	PC	98.54	788.32	201.57	1,612.58	2,400.90
2		4"X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 2 SINGLE-POLE 2p SWITCHES - THESY LINE - WHITE	INOVA	3	PC	181.04	543.12	327.56	862.67	1,525.79
3		3x#1 5mm² CORD - AFUMEX + 2P-T FEMALE INLINE PLUG - 15A	MICL	8	CJ	33.50	268.00	403.15	3,225.16	3,493.16
TOTAL COST										
							3,617.48		20,905.88	23,622.56

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL PANELS										
ELECTRICAL PANELS SUBTOTAL										
							17,000.00		5,766.76	22,766.76
1		QDF-01	VR7	1	CJ	7,000.00	7,000.00	1,845.36	1,845.36	8,845.36
2		QD-MED	VR7	1	CJ	10,000.00	10,000.00	3,921.39	3,921.39	13,921.39
TOTAL COST										
							17,000.00		5,766.76	22,766.76

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
SUMMARY OF PRICES FOR ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS										
FIRST FLOOR										
1		INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE FOR OUTLETS		1	VB		6,021.21		30,264.12	36,285.33
2		INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - LIGHTING		1	VB		3,617.48		20,005.08	23,622.56
3		INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - ELECTRICAL PANELS		1	VB		17,000.00		5,766.76	22,766.76
GENERAL COST										
							26,838.69		56,035.96	82,874.65

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS AND INFRASTRUCTURE - OUTLETS										
SECOND FLOOR										
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL										
							1,164.00		13,856.12	15,020.12
1		BOLTNUT/WASHER ø 1/4"	REAL PERFIL	350	CJ	0.84	294.00	15.12	5,291.28	5,585.28
2		REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE	INOVA	100	M	8.60	860.00	85.67	8,566.84	9,426.84
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL										
							2,476.11		7,605.34	10,081.45
1		COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX. #2.50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX	NAMBEI	126	M	4.54	572.04	15.12	1,904.86	2,476.90
2		COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX. #4.00mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX	NAMBEI	283	M	6.74	1,906.07	20.16	5,700.47	7,606.55
FINISHES SUBTOTAL										
							1,557.88		7,080.24	8,638.12
1		4"X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 OUTLET 2P-T-10A - MODEL THESY	INOVA	14	PC	44.16	618.24	201.57	2,822.02	3,440.26
2		4"X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 2 OUTLETS 2P-T-10A - MODEL THESY	INOVA	13	PC	72.28	939.64	327.56	4,256.22	5,197.86
TOTAL COST										
							5,189.99		28,543.70	33,733.69

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS - LIGHTING										
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL										
							1,159.58		11,540.04	12,699.62
1		REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE	INOVA	90	M	8.60	774.00	85.67	7,710.15	8,484.15
2		BOLTNUT/WASHER ø 1/4"	REAL PERFIL	100	CJ	0.84	84.00	15.12	1,511.79	1,595.79
3		4"X4" PVC OCTAGONAL BOX	INOVA	10	PC	26.40	264.00	201.57	2,015.73	2,279.73
4		4"X2" PVC BOX	INOVA	3	PC	5.86	17.58	100.79	302.36	319.94
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL										
							1,099.59		3,661.57	4,761.16
1		COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX. #2.50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX	NAMBEI	242	M	4.54	1,099.59	15.12	3,661.57	4,761.16
FINISHES SUBTOTAL										
							2,412.44		8,516.45	10,928.89
1		4"X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 SINGLE-POLE 2p SWITCH - THESY LINE - WHITE	INOVA	11	PC	98.54	1,083.94	201.57	2,217.30	3,301.24
2		4"X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 2 SINGLE-POLE 2p SWITCHES - THESY LINE - WHITE	INOVA	1	PC	626.00	626.00	251.97	251.97	1,077.97
3		3x#1 5mm² CORD - AFUMEX + 2P-T FEMALE INLINE PLUG - 15A	MICL	15	CJ	33.50	502.50	403.15	6,847.15	6,546.88
TOTAL COST										
							4,671.61		23,716.05	28,388.66

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS - AIR CONDITIONING										
							172.00		1,713.37	1,885.37
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL										
1		REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TKRE	NOVA	20	M	8.60	172.00	85.67	1,713.37	1,885.37
							544.80		1,814.15	2,358.95
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL										
1		COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX #2 50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX	NAMBEI	120	M	4.54	544.80	15.12	1,814.15	2,358.95
							716.80		3,527.52	4,244.32
TOTAL COST										

Página 4

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL PANELS										
							7,000.00		1,845.36	8,845.36
ELECTRICAL PANELS SUBTOTAL										
1		DDF-02	VR7	1	CJ	7,000.00	7,000.00	1,845.36	1,845.36	8,845.36
							7,000.00		1,845.36	8,845.36
TOTAL COST										

Página 5

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
SUMMARY OF PRICES FOR ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS SECOND FLOOR										
1		INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE FOR OUTLETS		1	VB		5,189.99		28,543.70	33,733.69
2		INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - LIGHTING		1	VB		4,671.61		23,718.05	28,389.66
3		INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - AIR CONDITIONING		1	VB		716.80		3,927.52	4,244.32
4		INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - ELECTRICAL PANELS		1	VB		7,000.00		1,845.36	8,845.36
							17,578.40		57,634.63	75,213.03
GENERAL COST										

Página 6

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS AND INFRASTRUCTURE - FEEDERS										
							618.60		15,673.85	16,492.45
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL										
1		KANAFLEX REINFORCED PVC FLEXIBLE CONDUIT - #1"	NOVA	18	M	8.24	123.60	352.75	5,291.28	5,414.88
2		KANAFLEX REINFORCED PVC FLEXIBLE CONDUIT - #2"	NOVA	38	M	16.50	495.00	352.75	10,582.56	11,077.56
							6,084.60		15,417.95	21,999.55
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL										
1		SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 25.0mm² - BLACK - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR- NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission	NAMBEI	72	M	38.62	2,779.84	85.67	6,168.12	8,948.76
2		SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 25.0mm² - BLUE - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR- NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission	NAMBEI	24	M	38.62	926.88	85.67	2,056.04	2,982.92
3		SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 25.0mm² - GREEN - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR- NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission	NAMBEI	24	M	38.62	926.88	85.67	2,056.04	2,982.92
4		SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 16.0mm² - BLACK - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR- NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission	NAMBEI	36	M	24.12	868.32	80.63	2,902.65	3,770.97
5		SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 16.0mm² - BLUE - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR- NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission	NAMBEI	12	M	24.12	289.44	80.63	967.55	1,256.99
6		SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 16.0mm² - GREEN - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR- NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission	NAMBEI	12	M	24.12	289.44	80.63	967.55	1,256.99
							118.32		4,541.79	4,659.11
TERMINALS SUBTOTAL										
1		COMPRESSION TERMINAL # 25.0mm²	NOVA	12	M	6.92	83.04	85.67	1,028.02	1,111.06
2		COMPRESSION TERMINAL # 16.0mm²	NOVA	6	M	5.88	35.28	80.63	483.77	519.05
							6,818.52		32,603.59	39,322.11
TOTAL COST										

Página 1

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
SUMMARY OF PRICES FOR ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS FEEDERS										
1		INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - FEEDERS		1	VB		6,818.52		32,603.59	39,322.11
							6,818.52		32,603.59	39,322.11
GENERAL COST										

Página 2

Total Value: 197,209.79

Scenario 2:

Figure 2: Organizational chart scenario 2

In this scenario, a more practical method was used, in which the project to be budgeted is received, then analyzed, measured, and counted using CAD commands. Often, it is not necessary to count each item individually, as a single command can provide the total number of selected outlets, for example. After this process, all quantities are entered into an existing spreadsheet that automatically calculates the final values for materials and labor, also allowing for the adjustment of O&P (overhead and profit).

In this case, the time required to take off quantities in CAD was 40 minutes, after which entering the quantities into the spreadsheet took approximately 25 minutes. Considering the process from start to the formalization of the budget for delivery, the average total time was 65 minutes.

After completing the entire process of quantity takeoff and entering data into the spreadsheet, a double-check was performed comparing the spreadsheet entries with the project. A total of 2 errors were identified: 1 related to the length of an infrastructure element and 1 related to an accessory of an infrastructure element.

Figure 3: Electrical infrastructure in 2D format (CAD).

Spreadsheet used for calculating materials and labor through the CAD method:

LABOR AND MATERIALS SUPPLY	
Manager:	Anonymous
Project:	Anonymous
Resp. Manag.:	

Item	Service	Quant.	Unit.	Sub MAT R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal R\$
PRICE SUMMARY OF ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE						
1	ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE - FIRST FLOOR	1	VB	27.011,51	56.503,69	83.515,20
2	ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE - SECOND FLOOR	1	VB	17.932,05	59.714,54	77.646,59
3	ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE - FEEDERS - GENERAL IMPLEMENTATION	1	VB	6.819,52	31.757,59	38.577,11
EXECUTION TIME (DAYS): 60						
PAYMENT METHOD : TO COMBINE						
CONSIDERATIONS:						
EXCLUSIONS:						
1 - luminaires, lamps, ballasts and accessories;						
2 - generator set, UPS, transformer, stabilizer and related accessories;						
3 - civil construction services in general;						
4 - structured cabling services, CCTV systems, access control, fire detection and alarm, sound, etc.						
GENERAL TOTAL				51.762,08	148.005,82	199.767,90

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal R\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS AND INFRASTRUCTURE - OUTLETS										
FIRST FLOOR										
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL							1.134,48		13.560,73	14.695,21
1	BOLT/NUT/WASHER # 1/4"		REAL PERFL	300	CJ	0,84	319,20	14,78	5.618,27	5.937,47
2	REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE		NOVA	95	M	8,60	815,20	83,78	7.942,46	8.757,66
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL							3.849,61		12.101,95	15.951,56
1	COPPER CABLE - FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX #2.50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX		NAMBEI	384	M	4,54	1.741,54	14,78	5.671,50	7.413,04
2	COPPER CABLE - FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX #4.00mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX		NAMBEI	70	M	6,74	471,80	19,71	1.379,93	1.851,73
3	COPPER CABLE - FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX #6.00mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX		NAMBEI	171	M	9,58	1.639,26	29,57	5.050,53	6.689,79
FINISHES SUBTOTAL							1.413,64		6.160,39	7.574,03
1	4"X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 OUTLET 2P-T-10A - MODEL THESY		NOVA	12	PC	44,16	529,92	197,13	2.365,59	2.895,51
2	4"X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 OUTLET 2P-T-20A - MODEL THESY		NOVA	3	PC	53,64	160,92	197,13	591,40	752,32
3	4"X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 2 OUTLETS 2P-T-10A - MODEL THESY		NOVA	10	PC	72,28	722,80	320,34	3.203,40	3.926,20
TOTAL COST							6.397,73		31.823,07	38.220,80

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal R\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS - LIGHTING										
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL							1.016,50		10.417,82	11.434,40
1	REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE		NOVA	79	M	8,60	679,40	83,78	6.618,72	7.298,12
2	BOLT/NUT/WASHER # 1/4"		REAL PERFL	110	CJ	0,84	92,40	14,78	1.629,34	1.718,74
3	4"X4" PVC OCTAGONAL BOX		NOVA	8	PC	28,40	227,20	197,13	1.577,06	1.804,26
4	4"X2" PVC BOX		NOVA	3	PC	5,69	17,55	98,57	295,70	313,25
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL							916,26		2.980,64	3.896,90
1	COPPER CABLE - FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX #2.50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX		NAMBEI	202	M	4,54	915,26	14,78	2.980,64	3.895,90
FINISHES SUBTOTAL							1.691,94		5.815,40	7.497,34
1	4"X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 SINGLE-POLE 2p SWITCH - THESY LINE - WHITE		NOVA	7	PC	98,54	689,78	197,13	1.379,93	2.069,71
2	4"X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 2 SINGLE-POLE 2p SWITCHES - THESY LINE - WHITE		NOVA	4	PC	181,04	724,16	320,34	1.281,36	2.005,52
3	3x#1.5mm² CORD - AFUMEX - 2P+T FEMALE BLUE PLUG - 15A		MICL	8	CJ	33,50	268,00	394,25	3.154,12	3.422,12
TOTAL COST							3.613,78		18.913,86	22.527,64

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal R\$
ELECTRICAL PANELS										
ELECTRICAL PANELS SUBTOTAL							17.000,00		5.766,76	22.766,76
1	QDF-01		VR7	1	CJ	7.000,00	7.000,00	1.845,36	1.845,36	8.845,36
2	QD-1ED		VR7	1	CJ	10.000,00	10.000,00	3.921,39	3.921,39	13.921,39
TOTAL COST							17.000,00		5.766,76	22.766,76

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Sub MAT R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal R\$
SUMMARY OF PRICES FOR ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS								
FIRST FLOOR								
1	INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE FOR OUTLETS			1	VB	6.397,73	31.823,07	38.220,80
2	INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - LIGHTING			1	VB	3.613,78	18.913,86	22.527,64
3	INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - ELECTRICAL PANELS			1	VB	17.000,00	5.766,76	22.766,76
GENERAL COST						27.011,51	56.503,69	83.515,20

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS AND INFRASTRUCTURE - OUTLETS										
SECOND FLOOR										
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL										
							1,295.04		14,926.86	16,221.90
1		BOLT/NUT/WASHER # 1/4"		350	CJ	0.84	294.00	14.78	5,174.72	5,468.72
2		REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE	NOVA	116	M	8.60	1,001.04	83.78	9,752.14	10,753.18
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL										
							2,478.11		7,437.80	9,915.91
1		COPPER CABLE FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION CLASS 70 °C FLEX #2.50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX	NAMBEI	126	M	4.54	572.04	14.78	1,862.90	2,434.94
2		COPPER CABLE FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION CLASS 70 °C FLEX #4.00mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX	NAMBEI	283	M	6.74	1,906.07	19.71	5,574.90	7,480.97
FINISHES SUBTOTAL										
							1,692.04		7,121.41	8,813.45
1		4X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 OUTLET 2P-T-10A - MODEL THESY	NOVA	15	PC	44.16	662.40	197.13	2,958.88	3,621.38
3		4X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 2 OUTLETS 2P-T-10A - MODEL THESY	NOVA	13	PC	72.28	939.64	320.34	4,164.42	5,104.06
TOTAL COST										
							5,375.10		29,486.07	34,861.26

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS - LIGHTING										
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL										
							1,236.58		12,167.90	13,404.57
1		REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE	NOVA	97	M	8.60	834.20	83.78	8,129.78	8,963.98
2		BOLT/NUT/WASHER # 1/4"	REAL PERFL	120	CJ	0.84	100.80	14.78	1,774.19	1,874.99
3		4X4" PVC OCTAGONAL BOX	NOVA	10	PC	28.40	284.00	197.13	1,971.32	2,255.32
4		4X2" PVC BOX	NOVA	3	PC	5.96	17.88	98.57	295.70	313.28
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL										
							1,099.59		3,580.91	4,680.50
1		COPPER CABLE FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION CLASS 70 °C FLEX #2.50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX	NAMBEI	242	M	4.54	1,099.59	14.78	3,580.91	4,680.50
FINISHES SUBTOTAL										
							2,412.44		8,328.84	10,741.28
1		4X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 SINGLE-POLE 2p SWITCH - THESY LINE - WHITE	NOVA	11	PC	86.54	1,033.94	197.13	2,168.46	3,252.40
2		4X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 2 SINGLE-POLE 2p SWITCHES - THESY LINE - WHITE	NOVA	1	PC	828.00	828.00	246.42	246.42	1,074.42
3		3x#1.5mm² CORD - AFUMEX + 2P+T FEMALE INLINE PLUG - 15A	MCL	15	CJ	33.50	502.50	394.26	5,913.97	6,416.47
TOTAL COST										
							4,748.61		24,077.74	28,826.35

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS - AIR CONDITIONING										
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL										
							258.00		2,513.44	2,771.44
1		REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE	NOVA	30	M	8.60	258.00	83.78	2,513.44	2,771.44
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL										
							550.25		1,791.93	2,342.18
1		COPPER CABLE FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION CLASS 70 °C FLEX #2.50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX	NAMBEI	121	M	4.54	550.25	14.78	1,791.93	2,342.18
TOTAL COST										
							808.25		4,305.37	5,113.62

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL PANELS										
ELECTRICAL PANELS SUBTOTAL										
							7,000.00		1,845.36	8,845.36
1		QDF-02	VR7	1	CJ	7,000.00	7,000.00	1,845.36	1,845.36	8,845.36
TOTAL COST										
							7,000.00		1,845.36	8,845.36

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
SUMMARY OF PRICES FOR ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS										
SECOND FLOOR										
1		INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE FOR OUTLETS		1	VB		5,375.10		29,486.07	34,861.26
2		INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - LIGHTING		1	VB		4,748.61		24,077.74	28,826.35
3		INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - AIR CONDITIONING		1	VB		808.25		4,305.37	5,113.62
4		INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - ELECTRICAL PANELS		1	VB		7,000.00		1,845.36	8,845.36
GENERAL COST										
							17,932.05		59,714.54	77,646.59

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS AND INFRASTRUCTURE - FEEDERS										
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL										
							618.60		15,524.17	16,142.77
1		KANAFLEX REINFORCED PVC FLEXIBLE CONDUIT - #1"	NOVA	15	M	8.24	123.60	344.98	5,174.72	5,298.32
2		KANAFLEX REINFORCED PVC FLEXIBLE CONDUIT - #2"	NOVA	30	M	16.50	495.00	344.98	10,349.45	10,844.45
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL										
							6,061.60		14,784.92	20,846.52
1		SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 25.0mm² - BLACK - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR- NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission	NAMBEI	72	M	38.62	2,780.64	83.78	6,032.25	8,812.89
2		SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 25.0mm² - BLUE - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR- NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission	NAMBEI	24	M	38.62	926.88	83.78	2,016.75	2,937.63
3		SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 25.0mm² - GREEN - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR- NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission	NAMBEI	24	M	38.62	926.88	83.78	2,016.75	2,937.63
4		SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 18.0mm² - BLACK - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR- NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission	NAMBEI	36	M	24.12	868.32	78.85	2,838.71	3,707.03
5		SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 18.0mm² - BLUE - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR- NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission	NAMBEI	12	M	24.12	289.44	78.85	946.24	1,235.68
6		SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 18.0mm² - GREEN - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR- NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission	NAMBEI	12	M	24.12	289.44	78.85	946.24	1,235.68
TERMINALS SUBTOTAL										
							118.32		1,478.49	1,596.81
1		COMPRESSION TERMINAL # 25.0mm²	NOVA	12	M	6.92	83.04	83.78	1,065.37	1,088.41
2		COMPRESSION TERMINAL # 18.0mm²	NOVA	6	M	5.88	35.28	78.85	473.12	508.40
TOTAL COST										
							6,818.52		31,787.59	38,606.11
SUMMARY OF PRICES FOR ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS										
FEEDERS										
1		INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - FEEDERS		1	VB		6,818.52		31,787.59	38,606.11
GENERAL COST										
							6,818.52		31,787.59	38,606.11

Total Value: 199,767.90

Scenario 3:

Figure 4: Organizational chart scenario 3

In this scenario, the most modern method was used, where the project to be estimated is received and, although an analysis may still occur, the quantities are already prepared along with the project. After this, all quantities are entered into an existing spreadsheet that automatically calculates the final values for materials and labor, also allowing for the adjustment of O&P (Overhead & Profit).

In this case, entering the quantities into the spreadsheet took approximately 30 minutes. Considering the process from start to the formalization of the budget for delivery, the average total time was 35 minutes.

After completing the entire process of quantity takeoff and entering data into the spreadsheet, a double-check was performed comparing the spreadsheet entries with the project, and a total of 0 errors were identified.

Figure 5: Electrical infrastructure in 3D format (Revit/BIM)

Spreadsheet used for calculating materials and labor through the BIM method:

versão 03 - DM
PL-VR73324-rev.00
27/09/2025

LABOR AND MATERIALS SUPPLY

Manager:	Anonymous
Project:	Anonymous
Resp. Manag.:	

Item	Service	Quant.	Unit.	Sub MAT R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
PRICE SUMMARY OF ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE						
1	ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE - FIRST FLOOR	1	VB	27.279,69	57.784,52	85.064,21
2	ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE - SECOND FLOOR	1	VB	18.281,49	61.748,84	80.030,32
3	ELECTRICAL INSTALLATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE - FEEDERS - GENERAL IMPLEMENTATION	1	VB	6.818,52	30.855,89	37.674,41
EXECUTION TIME (DAYS): 60 PAYMENT METHOD : TO COMBINE						
CONSIDERATIONS:						
EXCLUSIONS:						
1 - luminaires, lamps, ballasts and accessories.						
2 - generator set, UPS, transformer, stabilizer and related accessories.						
3 - civil construction services in general.						
4 - structured cabling services, CCTV systems, access control, fire detection and alarm, sound, etc.						
GENERAL TOTAL				52.379,70	160.389,24	202.768,94

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS AND INFRASTRUCTURE - OUTLETS										
FIRST FLOOR										
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL							1.134,48		13.163,26	14.297,74
1	BOLT/NUT/WASHER ø 1/4"		REAL PERFL	380	CJ	0,84	319,20	14,35	5.453,80	5.772,80
2	REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE		NOVA	95	M	8,60	815,28	81,33	7.709,67	8.524,95
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL							3.249,61		11.747,24	15.006,85
1	COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX. #2 50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX		NAMBEI	384	M	4,54	1.741,54	14,35	5.505,26	7.246,81
2	COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX. #4 00mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX		NAMBEI	70	M	6,74	471,80	19,14	1.339,48	1.811,28
3	COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX. #6 00mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX		NAMBEI	171	M	9,58	1.636,26	23,70	4.902,50	6.538,76
FINISHES SUBTOTAL							1.413,64		5.079,82	7.393,46
1	4"x2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 OUTLET 2P+T-10A - MODEL THESY		NOVA	12	PC	44,16	529,92	191,35	2.296,25	2.826,17
2	4"x2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 OUTLET 2P+T-20A - MODEL THESY		NOVA	3	PC	53,64	160,92	191,35	574,06	734,98
3	4"x2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 2 OUTLETS 2P+T-10A - MODEL THESY		NOVA	10	PC	72,28	722,80	310,95	3.109,51	3.832,31
TOTAL COST							6.397,73		30.890,33	37.288,06

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS - LIGHTING										
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL							1.251,26		12.206,49	13.457,75
1	REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE		NOVA	95	M	8,60	815,28	81,33	7.709,67	8.524,95
2	BOLT/NUT/WASHER ø 1/4"		REAL PERFL	160	CJ	0,84	134,40	14,35	2.296,25	2.430,65
3	4"x4" PVC OCTAGONAL BOX		NOVA	10	PC	28,40	284,00	191,35	1.913,54	2.197,54
4	4"x2" PVC BOX		NOVA	3	PC	5,86	17,58	95,68	287,03	304,61
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL							916,26		2.893,28	3.809,54
1	COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX. #2 50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX		NAMBEI	202	M	4,54	915,26	14,35	2.893,28	3.808,54
FINISHES SUBTOTAL							1.716,44		6.027,66	7.743,10
1	4"x2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 SINGLE-POLE 2ø SWITCH - THESY LNE - WHITE		NOVA	7	PC	98,54	689,78	191,35	1.339,48	2.029,28
2	4"x2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 2 SINGLE-POLE 2ø SWITCHES - THESY LNE - WHITE		NOVA	4	PC	181,04	724,16	310,95	1.243,80	1.967,96
3	3øx1 5mm CORD - AFUMEX - 2P+T FEMALE INLINE PLUG - 15A		MCL	9	CJ	33,50	301,50	382,71	3.444,38	3.745,88
TOTAL COST							3.881,96		21.127,43	25.009,40

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
ELECTRICAL PANELS										
ELECTRICAL PANELS SUBTOTAL							17.000,00		5.766,76	22.766,76
1	QDF-01		VR7	1	CJ	7.000,00	7.000,00	1.845,36	1.845,36	8.845,36
2	QD-MED		VR7	1	CJ	10.000,00	10.000,00	3.921,39	3.921,39	13.921,39
TOTAL COST							17.000,00		5.766,76	22.766,76

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$
SUMMARY OF PRICES FOR ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS										
FIRST FLOOR										
1	INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE FOR OUTLETS			1	VB		6.397,73		30.890,33	37.288,06
2	INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - LIGHTING			1	VB		3.881,96		21.127,43	25.009,40
3	INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - ELECTRICAL PANELS			1	VB		17.000,00		5.766,76	22.766,76
GENERAL COST							27.279,69		57.784,52	85.064,21

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$	
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS AND INFRASTRUCTURE - OUTLETS											
SECOND FLOOR											
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL							1,295.04		14,489.35	15,784.39	
1	BOLT/NUT/WASHER # 1/4"		REAL PERFL	350	CJ	0.84	294.00	14.35	5,023.05	5,317.05	
2	REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE		INOVA	116	M	8.60	1,001.04	81.33	9,466.30	10,467.34	
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL							2,478.11		7,218.80	9,697.91	
1	COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX #2.50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX		NAMBEI	126	M	4.54	572.04	14.35	1,808.30	2,380.34	
2	COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX #4.00mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX		NAMBEI	283	M	6.74	1,906.07	19.14	5,411.50	7,317.57	
FINISHES SUBTOTAL							1,602.04		6,912.68	8,514.72	
1	4X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 OUTLET 2P+T-10A - MODEL THESY		INOVA	15	PC	44.16	662.40	191.35	2,870.31	3,532.71	
2	4X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 2 OUTLETS 2P+T-10A - MODEL THESY		INOVA	13	PC	72.28	939.64	310.95	4,042.36	4,982.00	
TOTAL COST									5,375.19	28,621.82	33,997.02

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$	
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS - LIGHTING											
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL							1,519.02		14,776.38	16,295.40	
1	REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE		INOVA	116	M	8.60	1,001.04	81.33	9,466.30	10,467.34	
2	BOLT/NUT/WASHER # 1/4"		REAL PERFL	190	CJ	0.84	159.60	14.35	2,726.80	2,886.40	
3	4X4" PVC OCTAGONAL BOX		INOVA	12	PC	28.40	340.80	191.35	2,286.25	2,927.05	
4	4X2" PVC BOX		INOVA	3	PC	5.86	17.58	95.68	287.03	304.61	
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL							1,099.59		3,475.95	4,575.54	
1	COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX #2.50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX		NAMBEI	242	M	4.54	1,099.59	14.35	3,475.95	4,575.54	
FINISHES SUBTOTAL							2,479.44		8,850.14	11,329.58	
1	4X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 1 SINGLE-POLE 2P SWITCH - THESY LINE - WHITE		INOVA	11	PC	86.54	1,083.94	191.35	2,104.90	3,188.84	
2	4X2" WALL PLATE ASSEMBLY WITH 2 SINGLE-POLE 2P SWITCHES - THESY LINE - WHITE		INOVA	1	PC	326.00	326.00	239.19	239.19	1,065.19	
3	3x#1.5mm² CORD - AFUMEX + 2P+T FEMALE INLINE PLUG - 15A		MCL	17	CJ	33.50	569.50	382.71	6,506.05	7,075.55	
TOTAL COST									5,098.05	27,102.47	32,200.52

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$	
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS - AIR CONDITIONING											
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL							258.00		2,439.77	2,697.77	
1	REINFORCED FLEXIBLE CORRUGATED PVC CONDUIT ORANGE 3/4" - TIGRE		INOVA	30	M	8.60	258.00	81.33	2,439.77	2,697.77	
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL							550.25		1,739.41	2,289.66	
1	COPPER CABLE, FLAME-RETARDANT PVC INSULATION, CLASS 70 °C, FLEX #2.50mm² - 450/750V - NBR 13248 - AFUMEX		NAMBEI	121	M	4.54	550.25	14.35	1,739.41	2,289.66	
TOTAL COST									808.25	4,179.18	4,987.43

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$	
ELECTRICAL PANELS											
ELECTRICAL PANELS SUBTOTAL							7,000.00		1,845.36	8,845.36	
1	QDF-02		VR7	1	CJ	7,000.00	7,000.00	1,845.36	1,845.36	8,845.36	
TOTAL COST									7,000.00	1,845.36	8,845.36

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$	
SUMMARY OF PRICES FOR ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS											
SECOND FLOOR											
1	INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE FOR OUTLETS			1	VB		5,375.19		28,621.82	33,997.02	
2	INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - LIGHTING			1	VB		5,098.05		27,102.47	32,200.52	
3	INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - AIR CONDITIONING			1	VB		808.25		4,179.18	4,987.43	
4	INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - ELECTRICAL PANELS			1	VB		7,000.00		1,845.36	8,845.36	
GENERAL COST									16,281.49	61,748.84	80,030.32

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$	
ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS AND INFRASTRUCTURE - FEEDERS											
INFRASTRUCTURE SUBTOTAL							618.00		16,069.15	16,687.15	
1	KANAFLEX REINFORCED PVC FLEXIBLE CONDUIT - #1"		INOVA	15	M	9.24	123.60	334.87	5,023.05	5,146.65	
2	KANAFLEX REINFORCED PVC FLEXIBLE CONDUIT - #2"		INOVA	30	M	16.50	495.00	334.87	10,046.10	10,541.10	
CONDUCTORS SUBTOTAL							6,081.60		14,351.57	20,433.17	
1	SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 25.0mm² - BLACK - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR - NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission		NAMBEI	72	M	38.62	2,780.64	81.33	5,853.44	8,634.08	
2	SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 25.0mm² - BLUE - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR - NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission		NAMBEI	24	M	38.62	926.88	81.33	1,951.81	2,879.69	
3	SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 25.0mm² - GREEN - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR - NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission		NAMBEI	24	M	38.62	926.88	81.33	1,951.81	2,879.69	
4	SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 16.0mm² - BLACK - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR - NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission		NAMBEI	36	M	24.12	868.32	76.54	2,755.50	3,623.82	
5	SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 16.0mm² - BLUE - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR - NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission		NAMBEI	12	M	24.12	289.44	76.54	918.50	1,207.94	
6	SINGLE-CORE FLEXIBLE COPPER CABLE # 16.0mm² - GREEN - 0.6/1.0 KV - EPR - NBR 13248 - Low Smoke and Low Toxic Gas Emission		NAMBEI	12	M	24.12	289.44	76.54	918.50	1,207.94	
TERMINALS SUBTOTAL							110.32		1,435.16	1,545.48	
1	COMPRESSION TERMINAL # 25.0mm²		INOVA	12	M	6.92	83.04	81.33	975.91	1,058.95	
2	COMPRESSION TERMINAL # 16.0mm²		INOVA	6	M	5.88	35.28	76.54	459.25	494.53	
TOTAL COST									6,818.52	30,855.89	37,674.41

Group	Item	Service	Supplier	Quant.	Unit.	Unit MAT R\$	Sub MAT R\$	Unit LAB R\$	Sub LAB R\$	Subtotal r\$	
SUMMARY OF PRICES FOR ELECTRICAL INSTALLATIONS											
FEEDERS											
1	INSTALLATION ELECTRICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE - FEEDERS			1	VB		6,818.52		30,855.89	37,674.41	
GENERAL COST									6,818.52	30,855.89	37,674.41

Total Value: 202,768.94

6.2 Comparisons Between Each Scenario

Figure 6: Comparative graph of working time between the scenarios

Figure 7: Comparative graph of errors between the scenarios

Figure 8: Comparative graph of values in percentage between the scenarios

VALUES		DIFFERENCES		
SITUATION1	R\$ 197,209.79	MANUAL x CAD	R\$ 2,558.11	1.28%
SITUATION2	R\$ 199,767.90	CAD x BIM	R\$ 3,001.04	1.48%
SITUATION3	R\$ 202,768.94	BIM x MANUAL	R\$ 5,559.15	2.74%

All three scenarios were conducted in real conditions by the author of this thesis with the aim of scientifically reproducing the daily routine of an electrical cost estimator. Timed quantity takeoffs were performed using the same project for all three scenarios, with each takeoff carried out on different days to avoid direct influence from mental fatigue, in the same environment, and using the same manual and digital tools available in all cases.

There may be variations in individual speed, hardware performance, and project complexity. However, based on the simulations performed, it is possible to compare the execution time and the number of errors using the manual method, CAD, and BIM.

Comparing the three scenarios, a clear optimization in working time was observed from Scenario 1 to Scenario 3. The same trend is seen in error probability: with the manual method, and sometimes with CAD, it is common to “forget” to record some items, whereas in Scenario 3 this is considerably reduced.

Regarding the differences in values between spreadsheets, a 2.74% difference was noted between using the manual method in Scenario 1 and using the BIM method in Scenario 3, which in this case amounted to a difference of R\$ 5,559.15

Although this is a small project with a final value of R\$ 202,768.94, the difference may seem minor. However, if we extrapolate the same methods to a project worth R\$ 10,000,000.00, the same 2.74% difference would amount to R\$ 274,000.00. Therefore, the larger the project, the higher the potential for financial losses when not using the BIM methodology. Moreover, if the 2.74% error is an overestimation rather than an underestimation, it may not directly cause losses to the company, but it could certainly eliminate the company from competing successfully against competitors with more accurate budgeting methods.

Ma and Liu (2018) highlight that the use of BIM can reduce execution time for certain project phases by up to 30%, delivering a high return on investment (ROI) for construction companies that adopt the methodology.

These comparisons clearly demonstrate the advantages of BIM 5D, particularly regarding efficiency and data reliability. Although BIM requires higher initial training and investment, the medium- and long-term gains outweigh these barriers.

7. RESULTS

- Time Efficiency: BIM reduced the budgeting time by more than 70% compared to the manual method.
- Error Reduction: BIM eliminated the risk of omissions commonly found in manual processes and in 2D AutoCAD.
- Data Integration: Revit enabled real-time updates, with cost tables automatically reflecting project modifications.

These results reinforce the role of BIM as a facilitator of quality and control in the budgeting of electrical projects.

7.1 Detailed Results

Criterion	Manual	AutoCAD (2D)	BIM (Revit – 5D)
Takeoff time	High Item-by-item counting and measurement	Medium Using CAD commands	Low Automated takeoff
Precision of quantitative	Low Subject to human error during counting	Medium greater visualization and fewer errors	High Design-driven quantify
Ease of review	Low Re-do everything manually	Medium specific adjustments	High Model-linked tables
Project visualization	Need to print	2D view on screen	Full 3D with simulation
Budget integration	Manual Manual takeoff and spreadsheet input	Semi-automated (Excel) Accelerated quantify takeoff using CAD and Excel input	Total (dentro do Revit) Direct input into Excel
Error reduction	Low	Medium	High

7.2 Comparison of Task Reduction

Figure 9: Image of a comparative organizational chart showing task reduction

8. DISCUSSION

8.1 BIM in Electrical Budgeting

Three-dimensional modeling allows for the automatic extraction of quantity schedules directly from the project, containing information such as the number of outlets, luminaires, switches, conduits, and other elements. These data are accurate because they reflect exactly what has been modeled, eliminating the need for manual counts or external measurements. If the project is revised, the tables update automatically as the model is changed, ensuring consistency between the project and the material takeoff during budget review. This makes the process faster, standardized, and more reliable, contributing to a more consistent cost estimate, even though the final budget still requires manual entry of information into Excel.

From a financial perspective, BIM helps prevent overestimation, which would make the budget more expensive than necessary and potentially result in losing a bid. Conversely, underestimation can make a bid more competitive, increasing the chances of winning a contract, but it may also lead to losses and unexpected costs during material procurement and project execution.

8.2 BIM in Pre-Construction Phase of Electrical Projects

With the accuracy and precision of quantities extracted directly from the BIM model, the material procurement process becomes faster and more reliable, reducing delays and waste. The clear organization of items allows for advanced planning of purchases, ensuring that materials arrive on-site at the right time and in the correct quantities. This directly contributes to a safer, more predictable start of activities with less rework. When the project is followed faithfully, all specified materials are likely to be available throughout the construction process.

Moreover, this predictability aids in inventory control and supplier negotiations, allowing purchases to be made in stages or in strategic batches. Another benefit is the reduction of interruptions caused by supply failures, which positively impacts the project schedule. Efficient on-site material supply directly influences both the physical progress and financial management of the construction.

8.3 BIM durante a obra de elétrica

In the case of a company already integrated with the BIM methodology, the site supervisor or project engineer tends to replace traditional printed plans with digital devices such as tablets or lightweight laptops, which facilitate real-time consultation of the 3D model. This allows for a much clearer and more interactive reading of the project, especially in electrical installations, where conduit routing and positioning details are critical.

Through 3D visualization, the professional can precisely identify the path a conduit should follow within a wall or between slabs, correctly connecting switches, lighting points, and panels. This spatial understanding eliminates common ambiguities found in 2D drawings, which do not accurately represent heights, overlaps, or conflicts between systems. Using the model on-site also enables proactive solutions, avoids improvisation, and improves communication with the execution team. Additionally, any project revisions can be quickly updated and redistributed digitally, without the need for reprinting. Access to this information on-site enhances technical control and ensures fidelity to the original project design.

Figure 10: 3D image of the conduit route from the light point (octagonal box) to the switch inside the wall

8.4 BIM in post-construction for electrical systems

After the completion of a conventional construction project, it is common to require an “As-Built” project, which involves updating the executive design with all the changes made during execution. This process, although essential for documentation and future maintenance, demands additional time, specialized labor, and often rework to record modifications made on-site. With the application of the BIM methodology, this scenario changes significantly. Since the 3D model is already developed with a high level of detail and precision, and allows continuous monitoring throughout the construction, the need to produce a separate “As-Built” is reduced or even eliminated. As long as the model is faithfully followed during execution, on-site adjustments can be minimized, since the planning already accounts for clashes and coordination between disciplines. Moreover, any changes made can be updated directly in the model, maintaining the fidelity of the project without creating new drawings. Sacks et al. (2018) emphasize that BIM is not merely a graphical tool, but an integrated modeling environment that connects geometric and non-geometric information, making the design process more collaborative and less prone to errors. This accelerates the final delivery of services and technical documentation to the client, promoting a more efficient and transparent project closeout.

9. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This research allowed a detailed analysis of the application of Building Information Modeling (BIM), with software such as Revit serving as a powerful tool for the quantification and budgeting of electrical projects in residential, commercial, and industrial buildings. By comparing traditional methods, such as manual surveys and the use of 2D AutoCAD, with the process of extracting quantities through BIM, significant gains were observed in terms of accuracy, speed, organization, and reliability. The automatic generation of tables in Revit—even without complex plugin integrations or AI-based automation—already represents a meaningful advancement for the technical work of electrical engineers. The 3D model carries essential information about each element, transforming the project into a reliable basis for financial decision-making.

Direct extraction of quantities from the model reduces human errors, facilitates project review, and standardizes data collection. This standardization is particularly important in electrical engineering, where the detailing of components such as conduits, outlets, switches, finishes, panels, and circuits directly influences project cost and feasibility. BIM use, therefore, not only enhances communication between designers and estimators but also improves construction planning with better control over materials and labor. Even though the final step of transferring data to Excel spreadsheets remains manual in many offices, partial automation already represents a competitive advantage.

Implementing BIM goes beyond technological advancement: it constitutes a structural transformation in how buildings are designed, constructed, and operated, generating significant gains in efficiency, quality, and sustainability. At a national scale, BIM strengthens integration among government agencies, universities, and companies, promoting standardization, cost reduction, and greater competitiveness in the construction industry. At an international level, this study argues that BIM adoption may contribute to improved interoperability between projects, facilitate collaboration across different markets, and support more standardized digital practices within the construction sector. According to Khosrowshahi and Arayici (2012), the implementation of BIM played a key role in improving efficiency and coordination in public and private projects in United Kingdom, resulting in greater efficiency in both public and private projects.

In this context, the use of BIM—particularly in its 5D dimension, integrating costs with the 3D model—has proven decisive in budgeting electrical projects. The ability to automatically extract quantities, review costs in real time, and detect clashes before execution adds technical and financial value to the process. Through this method, BIM adoption already brings tangible benefits such as error reduction, increased productivity, and greater budget predictability. Furthermore, it enhances communication across disciplines and significantly reduces rework, promoting smarter and more collaborative construction.

In conclusion, on a global scale, BIM is no longer a trend but a tool that redefines quality standards in the construction industry. Technological advancement and digital maturity demonstrate that structured BIM adoption is strategically viable. With the consolidation of Revit for system modeling and the application of 5D BIM, the traditional workflow of exporting quantities to Excel still represents an area for optimization. One path is the use of plugins and software that streamline the quantity takeoff process, integrating Revit and automating spreadsheets.

Advancing toward artificial intelligence, machine learning algorithms can already perform predictive cost analyses based on historical data from previous projects. When applied to databases storing characteristics of similar projects (area, typology, electrical system, location, among others), these solutions can predict expected costs for new ventures with reasonable accuracy. Additionally, they can alert to significant budget deviations in real time when model changes directly impact cost estimates, supporting more technical and data-driven decision-making.

Finally, BIM implementation demonstrates clear and concrete benefits regardless of the economic context, whether in developed countries like the United States or emerging markets like Brazil. By integrating 3D modeling, automated quantity extraction, and 5D budgeting, BIM ensures greater financial accuracy, reducing waste, design errors, and losses due to execution failures. Standardization of information and partial workflow automation minimize rework, facilitate reviews, and make project data more reliable, promoting safer and more efficient planning. Concurrently, increasing integration with artificial intelligence enables predictive cost analyses, real-time deviation detection, and strategic decision support based on historical data, further

enhancing project reliability and accuracy. Beyond optimizing financial resources, BIM strengthens team communication and multidisciplinary coordination, fostering smarter and more collaborative construction. Thus, BIM consolidates itself as an indispensable tool for construction professionals and companies worldwide, capable of generating savings, reducing risks, and increasing competitiveness in any context, while redefining standards of quality and innovation in the sector.

REFERENCES

- Azhar, S. (2011). Building Information Modeling (BIM): Trends, benefits, risks, and challenges for the AEC industry. *Leadership and Management in Engineering*, 11(3), 241–252.
[https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)LM.1943-5630.0000127](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)LM.1943-5630.0000127)
- Abanda, F.H., Vidalakis, C., Oti, A.H. & Tah, J.H.M. (2015). A critical analysis of Building Information Modelling systems used in construction projects. *Advances in Engineering Software*, 90, 183–201.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advengsoft.2015.08.009>
- Akponeware, A.O. & Adamu, Z.A. (2017). Clash detection or clash avoidance? An investigation into coordination problems in 3D BIM. *Buildings*, 7(3), 75. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings7030075>
- Aranda-Mena, G., Crawford, J., Chevez, A. & Froese, T. (2009). Building information modelling demystified. *International Journal of Managing Projects in Business*, 2(3), 419–434.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/17538370910971063>
- Barlish, K. & Sullivan, K. (2012). How to measure the benefits of BIM. *Automation in Construction*, 24, 149–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2012.02.008>
- Becerik-Gerber, B. & Rice, S. (2010). The perceived value of building information modeling in the U.S. building industry. *Journal of Information Technology in Construction*, 15, 185–201.
<http://www.itcon.org/2010/15>
- Bryde, D., Broquetas, M. & Volm, J.M. (2013). The project benefits of Building Information Modelling (BIM). *International Journal of Project Management*, 31(7), 971–980.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2012.12.001>
- Eastman, C., Teicholz, P., Sacks, R. & Liston, K. (2018). *BIM Handbook*. 3rd ed. Wiley.
- Ghaffarianhoseini, A. et al. (2017). BIM uptake: Benefits, risks and challenges. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 75, 1046–1053. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.11.083>
- Khanzode, A., Fischer, M. & Reed, D. (2008). Benefits of implementing VDC technologies for MEP coordination. *ITcon*, 13, 324–342. <http://www.itcon.org/2008/22>
- Khosrowshahi, F. & Arayici, Y. (2012). Roadmap for BIM implementation in the UK. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 19(6), 610–635.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/09699981211277531>
- Lu, W., Fung, A., Peng, Y., Liang, C. & Rowlinson, S. (2015). Cost-benefit analysis of BIM implementation in electrical and mechanical works. *Automation in Construction*, 57, 59–70.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2015.04.007>

Ma, Z. & Liu, Z. (2018). Quantification of BIM benefits and ROI. *Automation in Construction*, 92, 284–292.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2018.04.005>

Succar, B. (2009). Building information modelling framework. *Automation in Construction*, 18(3), 357–375.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2008.10.003>

Volk, R., Stengel, J. & Schultmann, F. (2014). BIM for existing buildings. *Automation in Construction*, 38, 109–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2013.10.023>